

Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide as a Gravimetric Reagent for Manganese(II)

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Manganese(II) has been quantitatively precipitated with benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide and weighed as $Mn(C_{15}H_{11}O_4N_2)_2$ after drying at 120°. The pH of precipitation is 6.5-8.0. The presence of Ag^+ , Tl^+ , citric acid, sulphosalicylate, tartrate and iodide do not interfere in the determination. Citrate has been used to mask Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and VO^{2+} , sulphosalicylic acid for Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Fe^{3+} , tartrate for Pb^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{6+} , UO_2^{2+} and WO_4^{2-} and iodide for Hg^{2+} in the quantitative separation of manganese from these ions. The relative standard deviation is $\pm 0.21\%$.

THE bonding of manganese(II) is mainly ionic and the tendency of formation of complexes with neutral ligands including oxygen containing anions is very little¹. Thus, there are only very few organic reagents like 8-quinolinol², quinaldine acid³ and thioanilide with which manganese(II) can be determined and oxidation to permanganate is more convenient for this purpose.

However, benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide which has been first used as a gravimetric reagent for beryllium⁴ and subsequently for several other metal ions has now been successfully used in the determination of manganese(II) from near neutral solutions.

Experimental

Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide : The reagent was prepared in the laboratory⁵ and a fresh solution containing 0.18-0.22 g of it in 15 ml aqueous ethanol was prepared before use.

Manganese (II) Solution : Manganese (II) chloride (BDH) was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and suitably diluted. The metal content was determined titrimetrically after oxidation to permanganate.

All the other chemicals used were of A. R. or G. R. grade.

Apparatus :

A battery operated bench model Cambridge pH-meter was used to measure the acidity and a photorecording Metriplex Derivatograph OD-102 (Hungary) was used for the thermogravimetric studies. Magnetic susceptibility was measured in a modified electromagnetic microbalance⁷.

Procedure :

An aliquot of the stock solution containing 6 to 16 mg of manganese diluted to 150 ml with water was heated almost to boiling after the pH was adjusted to 4.0-4.5 with sodium acetate (5%) solution. The reagent solution was added slowly with stirring. The yellow manganese(II)-benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide complex was formed instantly on raising the pH to 6.5-8.0 with aqueous 2N ammonia. The precipitate was filtered through a sintered glass crucible of fine porosity after digesting on a hot water bath for 20 to 30 minutes, washed first with hot water (70-80°) and finally with 30 ml of 20% ethanol. This was weighed as $Mn(C_{15}H_{11}O_4N_2)_2$ after drying at 120°. The factor of the metal in the complex was 0.0884. The results of these determinations are given in Table 1.

TABLE—1 DETERMINATION OF MANGANESE(II)

Mn taken (mg)	Wt. of complex (mg)	Mn found, (mg)	Rel.error. (%)
6.33	72.0, 71.6	6.36, 6.32	+0.47, -0.15
10.56	119.5, 119.3	10.56, 10.54	nil -0.18
16.88	190.8, 191.2	16.86, 16.90	-0.11, +0.11

Separation from Diverse Ions :

When manganese(II) was precipitated from solutions containing other metal ions, a suitable masking agent, e.g. citric acid (1 g), sulphosalicylic acid (0.5 g), sodium potassium tartrate (1 g) or potassium iodide (0.1 g) was added before the addition of the reagent and the pH was finally adjusted between 7.5 and 8.0 otherwise the procedure was same as described above. Separation of manganese from reasonable amounts of Ag^+ or Tl^+ was possible using benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide as the precipitant. However, 1 g of citric acid was used to mask Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , VO^{2+} and Zn^{2+} and 0.5 g sulphosalicylic acid

for Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} . Manganese was precipitated in the presence of Pb^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} and WO_4^{2-} using 1 g of sodium potassium tartrate as the masking agent. Hg_2^{2+} was masked with 0.1 g of potassium iodide. In these experiments generally the diverse ions taken were about four times the amount of manganese (II). However, in case of bismuth and aluminium the amounts were lower as otherwise the relative error was beyond $\pm 0.5\%$. The results of these separations are given in Table 2.

metric (DTG) curves recorded have been presented in Figure 1.

The complex was found to be stable upto 220° , when a rapid exothermic decomposition took place and a loss of about 39% in weight was recorded. At 300° another exothermic change was noted, which was somewhat less rapid than the first one. The oxidation to the oxide stage was complete at 500° . The calculated loss for conversion to MnO_2 was 86%, while the experimental value (85%) was

TABLE-2 SEPARATION OF MANGANESE FROM DIVERSE IONS MANGANESE(II) TAKEN : 10.56 MG

Diverse ions (mg)	Masking agent	Wt. of complex (mg)	Mn found (mg)	Rel. error (%)
Ag^+ , 40	-	119.6, 119.3	10.57, 10.54	+0.09, -0.18
Ti^+ , 40	-	119.4, 119.5	10.56, 10.56	-0.09, nil
Hg_2^{2+} , 40	a	119.4, 119.7	10.55, 10.58	-0.09, +0.18
Cu^{2+} , 40	b	119.6, 119.1	10.57, 10.52	+0.09, -0.37
Cd^{2+} , 40	b	119.5, 119.2	10.56, 10.53	nil, -0.28
Zn^{2+} , 40	b	119.5, 119.4	10.56, 10.55	nil, -0.09
VO^{2+} , 40	b	119.2, 119.4	10.53, 10.55	-0.28, -0.09
Ni^{2+} , 40	c	119.7, 119.9	10.58, 10.60	+0.18, +0.37
Co^{2+} , 40	c	119.8, 119.4	10.59, 10.55	+0.28, -0.09
Fe^{3+} , 40	c	119.5, 119.2	10.56, 10.53	nil, -0.28
Pb^{2+} , 40	d	119.3, 119.7	10.54, 10.58	-0.18, +0.18
Bi^{3+} , 20	d	119.7, 119.8	10.58, 10.59	+0.18, +0.28
Al^{3+} , 30	d	119.6, 119.5	10.57, 10.56	-0.09, nil
Cr^{3+} , 40	d	119.1, 119.4	10.52, 10.55	-0.37, -0.09
UO_2^{2+} , 40	d	119.7, 119.4	10.58, 10.55	+0.18, -0.09
WO_4^{2-} , 40	d	119.9, 119.7	10.60, 10.58	+0.37, +0.18

(a) Potassium iodide, (b) Citric acid, (c) Sulphosalicylic acid, (d) Sodium potassium tartrate

Results and Discussion

Properties and Composition of the Complex :

The yellowish coloured complex is practically insoluble in ethanol, though soluble in acetone, isobutylmethylketone, chloroform and tributylphosphate. The pure complex was analysed for nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method (using glucose for the reduction of nitro group) and for manganese. The experimental results, Mn (calc. 8.84%, found 8.90, 8.81%) and N (calc. 9.01%, found 8.91, 8.95%) indicated the formula to be $\text{Mn}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2)_2$.

Magnetic Data :

The manganese(II)-bis-benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide chelate was found to be paramagnetic. The molar magnetic susceptibility ($\xi_m = 12690 \times 10^{-6}$ cgs unit) and $\mu = 5.61$ B. M. was in agreement to the expected value.

Thermal Decomposition Studies :

The oven-dried (120°) sample of manganese(II)-benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide complex (100 mg) with Al_2O_3 was subjected to heating at the rate of 12° per min. in air. The weight change (TG), differential thermal analysis (DTA) and differential thermogravi-

Fig. 1 Thermal decomposition curves of Manganese(II)-Benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide.

metric curves recorded have been presented in Figure 1. The complex was found to be stable upto 220° , when a rapid exothermic decomposition took place and a loss of about 39% in weight was recorded. At 300° another exothermic change was noted, which was somewhat less rapid than the first one. The oxidation to the oxide stage was complete at 500° . The calculated loss for conversion to MnO_2 was 86%, while the experimental value (85%) was

Effect of pH and Concentration of the Reagent :

Experiments on the precipitation of manganese from solutions adjusted to varying pH showed that the process was quantitative in the range 6.5 to 8.0.

The precipitation of manganese was carried out at fixed pH value (7.0) using varied amounts of the reagent, maintaining all other conditions identical. For the complete precipitation at least three times the reagent theoretically calculated was required.

Effect of Sequestering Agents :

The determination of manganese (II) was possible in the presence of citric or ascorbic acid, sulphosalicylic acid, tartrate and potassium iodide. However, the precipitation was prevented in the presence of Mg-EDTA and fluoride tartaric acid.

References

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